

ESTIMATION OF ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF LCF-PP/PANI-COMPLEX BLENDS

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SUMMARY: The aim of this study is to model the electrical conductivity of long carbon fibre (LCF) reinforced polypropylene (PP) composites and their blends with an electrically conductive polyaniline-complex (PANI-complex). A Fibre Contact Model is used to describe the electrical conductivity and to model the synergy effect between the two conductive components. This structure-oriented theory also considers the microstructural parameters, such as fibre length, orientation and concentration. The studied PANI-complex network is supposed to originate from processing induced PANI-complex fibrils, which are characterised in their dimensions and orientation. The predicted data for LCF-PP and PP/PANI-complex blends are in good agreement with the experimental results. By using an “increased conductive pathways” method, it is possible to model the synergy effect between LCF and PANI-complex. In this method it is assumed that the LCFs build a backbone of conductivity and the PANI-complex forms additional conductive pathways between them. Again the predictions are in good agreement with the experimental data.

KEYWORDS: CFRP, electrical properties, modelling, synergy effect, PANI-complex

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic polymers are traditionally used as electrically insulating materials. In order to make them electrically conductive, continuous pathways of electrically conductive particles in them must be established. For this purpose electrically conductive fillers, such as carbon black, carbon fibres, metal powder and metal fibres can be used. Another way for making normal insulating polymers electrically conductive is blending them with another electrically conductive polymer. At a low filler loading, the particles are homogeneously distributed in the insulating matrix without any contacts between adjacent filler particles. The conductivity of this composite is comparable to that of the matrix polymer. With rising filler concentration, however, clusters of filler particles begin to form and in these clusters the filler particles are in contact with each other. At a certain critical filler concentration, the growing clusters reach a size which enables a contact between them; a continuous network structure of the conducting filler is formed. This network formation can be detected as a drastic increase in the electrical conductivity of the composite. The abrupt increase in electrical conductivity is called the

percolation threshold of the (filler) material. At loadings above the critical level, the conductivity reaches a plateau and does not rise significantly with further addition of filler.

The existing models for predicting the electrical conductivity of this kind of materials can be subdivided into percolation theories and non-percolation theories (thermodynamic models, geometrical models and structure-oriented models). The general basis of the percolation theory is the fact that the conductivity of a composite dramatically increases at a certain fibre concentration (the percolation threshold). It can be used for modelling the electrical behaviour of a composite material and for predicting the percolation threshold itself [1-7]. The percolation theory is a statistical method and it calculates whether particles have contact with each other or not. A similar theoretical model can also be used to model e.g. the progress of a forest fire.

From the engineer's point of view the most promising models for predicting the electrical conductivity are the structure-oriented ones. The latter are based on microstructural data such as fibre orientation, length, and packing arrangement [8-16]. Most of these theories predict either the conductivity of the matrix or of the filler, but they do not take into account the percolation threshold. Weber and Kamal [14, 16] have evaluated new models which use microstructural data to predict the volume resistivity of a composite. The End-to-End Model (EEM) relates resistivity to the concentration and orientation of fibres by assuming a perfect fibre to fibre contact. In the Fiber Contact Model (FCM) the effects of both fibre to fibre contact and fibre length on the composite resistivity are additionally taken into account. A good agreement between predictions and experimental data for polypropylene composites reinforced with nickel-coated graphite fibres has been found [16].

The aim of this study is to model the electrical conductivity of long carbon fibre (LCF) reinforced polypropylene (PP) / polyaniline-complex (PANI-complex) blends. Of special consideration is the synergy effect between two electrically conductive components (LCF and PANI-complex) with regards to the electrical conductivity of their blends.

MODEL FOR PREDICTING THE ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY

The Fibre Contact Model (FCM) of Weber and Kamal [16] can be used for calculating the volume resistivity of fibre reinforced composites. The model is based on the studies of Batchelor and O'Brian [15] of thermal and electrical conductivities of particle-filled materials. Weber and Kamal [16] have developed the model further for fibre reinforced materials. It takes into account microstructural parameters, such as filler concentration and dimensions, aspect ratio and orientation of fibres. In the model of Weber and Kamal the conductivity of the matrix is estimated to be so low that it does not have any influence on the conductivity of the composites. In this study the equations are further developed so that they enable the calculation of electrical conductivity of the composite by taking into account also the electrical conductivity of the matrix. The latter is necessary when the synergy effect between fibres and PANI-complex has to be considered. The electrical conductivity can be defined as

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_m + \left[\frac{4}{\pi} * \left(\frac{d_c}{d} * \frac{l}{d} * \cos^2 \theta \right) * (\phi_p \sigma_f) * X \right] \quad (1)$$

in which

σ_c = conductivity of composite

σ_m = conductivity of matrix
 σ_f = conductivity of fibres
 d_c = diameter of circle of contact
 d = diameter of fibre
 l = average fibre length
 θ = orientation angle of fibre
(ϕ_p and X are explained below)

In the model it is assumed that a contact between fibres is not a perfect end-to-end contact, but rather an end-to-body or body-to-body type. The area of contact for these two cases is much smaller than in perfect end-to-end alignment, which therefore has an effect on the global conductivity of the composite. Besides, the FCM (Fibre Contact Model) is based on the fact that the particles have a flat circle of contact. The diameter of this contact circle d_c , is obviously a small number, but it is not possible to accurately measure this value. The value can be estimated by fitting the experimental data to the model calculations and then using this value for all other samples with different fibre loadings.

The symbol ϕ_p shows the volume fraction of fibres participating in the formation of electrical conductive pathways. Only the fibres forming the conducting network have an influence on the electrical conductivity. The rest of the fibres are surrounded by the matrix and do not improve the conductivity. The term ϕ_p can be written

$$\phi_p = \beta \phi_f \quad (2)$$

where ϕ_f is the volume fraction of fibres and β is a factor showing which parts of the fibres are participating in the conductive network. At volume fractions below the percolation threshold (critical concentration ϕ_{crit}), β is zero, because the fibres do not have contact with each other. A ‘‘saturated’’ volume fraction ϕ_t , in which sufficient enough fibres are participating to create at least one perfectly conductive pathway, is estimated by using the results of electrical conductivity measurements obtained with higher fibre content. At volume fractions greater than ϕ_t , β is 1 and ϕ_p will be equal to ϕ_f . For concentrations within the range of $\phi_{crit} < \phi_f < \phi_t$, β can be calculated in the following way:

$$\beta = \frac{\phi_f - \phi_{crit}}{\phi_t - \phi_{crit}} \quad (3)$$

A value of ϕ_t , at which β will be equal to 1, and ϕ_{crit} is obtained from the experimental data.

The symbol X is a factor depending on the contact number of fibres. Weber et. al. [16] have found a mathematical relation between X and m

$$X = 0.59 + 0.15 * m \quad (4)$$

where m is the number of contacts. It can be calculated by

$$m = m_{max} \left(\frac{\phi_p}{\phi_t} \right) \quad (5)$$

For all cases, the maximum number of contacts m_{max} is assumed to be 15 [16].

EXPERIMENTAL

Samples of LCF-PP/PANI-complex blends with different concentrations of LCF and PANI-complex were injection moulded into plates (with the dimensions of 80*80*2 mm³) and into test bars according to DIN EN61. The barrel temperatures were kept in all cases under 225°C in order to prevent degradation of the PANI-complex. The injection moulding parameters were maintained on a constant level in order to obtain similar fibre orientation patterns and fibre length distributions.

The electrical conductivity of the composites was determined with a 2-point technique, after removing the thin polymer skin layer, due to the injection moulding process. In addition, surface resistivity measurements on original samples (without removal of the polymer skin layer) were carried out (according to ASTM D-257). For the simulation purpose, the fibre content, length and orientation as well as the dimensions and orientation of PANI-complex droplets in the samples were studied. The fibre content was determined by burning samples at 500°C, and the fibre length was measured from the residue of the combustion by using light optical microscopy. Fibre orientation studies on polished cross-sections of the samples were carried out using light optical microscopy linked to an image analyser. The same analysis technique was used for determining the dimensions and orientation of PANI-complex droplets in thin sections, cut from the test bars by the use of a microtome.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

LCF-PP-Composites and PP/PANI-Complex-Blends

The electrical conductivities of LCF- and PANI-complex-blends are of different types. LCFs are fibres functioning as reinforcement in the matrix and increasing the electrical conductivity of the composites. The PANI-complex forms together with the matrix an immiscible polymer blend. The high shear forces near the surface region during injection moulding cause the dispersed PANI-droplets to deform into elongated droplets or fibrils, which finally form the conductive network [17]. This network structure can be seen in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Electrically conductive PANI-complex network structure in a PP-matrix.

These elongated droplets are assumed to function like fibres, and their orientation and dimensions can be measured. Table 1 presents these values as well as the values of the constant parameters used in the modelling of the electrical conductivity of LCF- and PANI-complex-blends.

Table 1: Values of parameters used in Fibre Contact Model.

Parameter	Abbr.	LCF	PANI-complex
Electrical conductivity of PP [S/cm]	σ_m	$5 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-14}$
Electrical conductivity of LCF [S/cm]	σ_f	$1 \cdot 10^3$	
Electrical conductivity of PANI [S/cm]	σ_{PANI}		$1 \cdot 10^0$
Critical filler content [vol.-%]	ϕ_{crit}	2,7	6.3
Fibre diameter [μm]	d	7	1
Average fibre length [μm]	l	50	100
Orientation angle of filler [$^\circ$]	θ	7	10

The critical filler contents were measured experimentally. Different authors have studied the critical fibre concentration theoretically by using percolation models and Monte-Carlo simulations [2-4]. They have shown that the percolation threshold depends on the fibre aspect ratio in the case of a random fibre orientation; the longer the fibres are, the lower is the percolation threshold. When all the fibres are aligned in one direction, the critical concentration has a constant value of 22 vol.-%. In the case studied here, carbon fibres are oriented nearly aligned and have an aspect ratio of about 7 ($l/d = 50/7$). According to Munson-McGee [4] that equals to a critical concentration of 13.5 vol.-%, which is, however, much higher than the critical concentration measured in these experiments. To reach the experimental threshold, the fibre aspect ratio should be about 80, which means an average fibre length of 560 μm would be needed. In fact, in the fibre length measurements also fibres of this length were found, although the majority of fibres was clearly shorter [18]. On the other hand, also longer fibres up to 3000 μm survived during the injection moulding process, which obviously compensated the negative contribution of the shorter fibres, so that, at the end, the measured percolation threshold could be verified. Besides the fibres, the experimental critical concentration of the PANI-complex is in agreement with the theoretical studies of Tanner [19].

From the theory, the saturated fibre content ϕ_t was estimated to be 11.5 vol.-% in the case of LCF and 26 vol.-% in the case of the PANI-complex [19, 20]. The number of contacts, m, was assumed to vary from a minimum of 2 to a maximum of 15. At loadings near the percolation threshold, each fibre has to have a minimum number of contacts, which is two. The maximum is reached at the saturated fibre content. For the ratio of the contact diameter to the fibre diameter, d_c/d , a value of $3 \cdot 10^{-6}$ for all of the LCF-composites and a value of $3 \cdot 10^{-7}$ for all of the PANI-complex –blends was used.

Fig. 2 compares the experimental electrical conductivity values with the model predictions. The experimental results of the electrical conductivity measurements verify the expected increase in conductivity with increasing filler content. When the percolation threshold is reached, the conductivity increases quickly, but maintains on a rather constant level after further addition of the filler components. In the case of LCF it was raised from the level of 10^{-13} S/cm (for neat PP) to 10^{-5} S/cm for PP with 4.3 vol.-% LCF (equal to 8 wt-% LCF). An abrupt percolation threshold of LCF could be observed at 2.7 vol.-% LCF. The experimental

percolation threshold of the PANI-complex was much smoother than that of the LCF. It was observed at 7.5 vol.-% of the PANI-complex. By using 21.5 vol.-% PANI-complex (equal to 25 wt.-% PANI-complex) an electrical conductivity of $5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ S/cm was reached. This is close to the volume fraction for “saturation”, ϕ_t , which was calculated as to be 26 vol.-%.

Fig. 2: Comparison between fibre contact model predictions and experimental data for LCF-PP-composites and PP/PANI-complex-blends.

The theoretical predictions of the electrical conductivity are in good agreement with the experimental results. In the theoretical predictions below the percolation threshold, the conductivity was assumed to be on the level of the non-filled PP-matrix. In the case of LCF, the increase of electrical conductivity was accurately predicted, but in the case of the PANI-complex the model did not take into account the “smoother” percolation threshold (subject of future consideration). Yet, the model showed good agreement of the electrical conductivity below and above the percolation threshold. It can be concluded that this model can also be used for the PANI-complex, when microstructural parameters of the blend can be defined.

Electrical Conductivity and Synergy Effects in LCF-PP/PANI-Complex-Composites

Fig. 3 shows for the PP-composites, filled with both LCF and PANI-complex, the specific surface resistivity measurements after transforming the data into electrical conductivity values. The results show a synergy effect between the PANI-complex and the LCF; the abrupt increase in the conductivity between 2.1 and 3.2 vol.-% was significantly reduced, and the conductivity of samples with 3.2 and 4.3 vol.-% CF could be increased by two orders of magnitude, using the additional PANI-complex. Furthermore, the percolation threshold could be moved towards a reduced fibre content. Already a low amount of the PANI-complex (4.1 vol.-%) was enough to increase the electrical conductivity.

The model was also used for blends consisting of two electrically conductive parts in order to model the synergy effect mentioned above. When the materials are examined in the

longitudinal direction, two different network structures can be observed; one was produced by the carbon fibres, while the other one originated from the PANI-complex. In the modelling it is assumed that these two network structures overlap. In the double network the electric charges have more possibilities to move. The levels of the conductivities of the carbon fibres (10^3 S/cm), the PANI-complex (10^0 S/cm) and the insulating matrix (10^{-13} S/cm) show significant differences. Due to the high conductivity of the carbon fibres it is assumed that they are mainly responsible for the conductivity of the composite. Therefore the microstructural parameters of LCF, such as fibre length, diameter and orientation, are used in the modelling of the synergy effect. Furthermore, the PP/PANI-complex-blend is assumed to form the electrically conductive matrix of the composite with LCF. In this point the developed model is different from the model of Weber and Kamal [16]. The latter assumes that the matrix does not contribute to the conductivity of the composite.

Fig. 3: Electrical conductivity of LCF-PP/PANI-complex-blends.

It is further assumed that the PANI-complex forms additional conducting pathways between carbon fibres and thus increases the number of conductive pathways in the LCF-composite. That means also that the percolation concentration is shifted, correspondingly, towards smaller concentrations. The critical percolation threshold for LCF-PP/PANI-complex-blends was determined experimentally at 1.8 vol.-%, compared to 2.7 vol.-% for LCF only and 6.3 vol.-% for the PANI-complex only. The shifted percolation threshold can be determined also theoretically by using the two latter concentrations and the theory of the multiple percolation [6]. According to this theory, the critical concentration can be shifted towards lower fibre contents when the number of components in a polymer matrix increases. The new critical volume fraction of LCF ϕ_{f^*} in the PP/PANI-complex blend can be calculated in the following way:

$$\phi_{f^*} = \phi_f \phi_{PANI} \quad (6)$$

The experimentally measured value of critical concentration (1.8 vol.-%) is in agreement with the theoretical value of 1.7 vol.-%.

An increase in the number of electrically conductive pathways is taken into account in the factors ϕ , β and m in the following way ($\phi > \phi_{crit}$):

$$\phi_{tot} = \phi_{CF} + \phi_{PANI} \quad (7)$$

$$\beta_{tot} = \beta_{CF} + \beta_{PANI} \quad (8)$$

$$m_{max_{tot}} = m_{max_{CF}} + m_{max_{PANI}} \quad (9)$$

The values of β_{PANI} and $m_{max_{PANI}}$ were determined at PANI-complex contents of 4.1, 6.3 and 8.4 vol.-%.

With these assumptions it is possible to model the synergy effect regarding the electrical conductivity, and the results of the modelling are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Comparison between theoretical predictions and experimental results of electrical conductivity of LCF-PP/PANI-complex-blends.

Below the percolation threshold the model shows a constant conductivity value of the matrix, in the case 0 and 4.1 vol.-% PANI-complex the value of PP, and in the two other cases the value of the PP/PANI-complex-blend. Within this range of carbon fibre content, the CF do not form a conductive network. The synergy effect became evident when the percolation threshold was moved towards a reduced carbon fibre content when using the PANI-complex. The developed “increased conductive pathways”-method can predict the electrical conductivity very well, and the predictions are again in agreement with the experimental results. It suggests the validity of the basic approach employed in developing the model and estimating the critical parameters on the basis of detailed material characterisation.

CONCLUSIONS

The electrical conductivity of LCF-PP/PANI-complex-blends was studied. A synergy effect regarding the electrical conductivity was observed; the abrupt increase in the conductivity was reduced and the conductivity could be increased by two orders of magnitude, using PANI-complex. Furthermore, the percolation threshold could be moved towards a reduced fibre content.

The Fibre Contact Model was used to model the electrical conductivity of the blends studied. This model takes into account the microstructural parameters, such as fibre length, orientation and concentration. At first it was used to predict the conductivity of LCF-PP-composites and PP/PANI-complex-blends, separately. The PANI-complex network was a structure consisting of processing induced fibre like PANI-complex-chains, whose orientation and dimensions could be measured. The theoretical predictions were in agreement with the experimental results.

Furthermore, the model was developed to predict the conductivity of LCF-PP/PANI-complex blends and the synergy effects in them. The carbon fibre network was assumed to be the backbone of the electrical conductivity. The PANI-complex was supposed to form additional conductive pathways between the carbon fibres, which would make a charge transport possible already below the percolation threshold of LCF. By using an "increased conductive pathways"-method, the synergy effect between LCF and PANI-complex regarding the conductivity could be predicted.

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